

EVALUATION OF MECHANICAL AND TRIBOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF ALUMINIUM AND MAGNESIUM COMPOSITE ALLOY BY STIR CASTING METHOD

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ABSTRACT

AA6061 is a heat-treatable aluminium alloy widely used in various industrial applications due to its excellent combination of mechanical properties, corrosion resistance, and weldability. This alloy belongs to the 6xxx series of aluminium alloys, characterized by magnesium and silicon as the major alloying elements. The microstructure of AA6061 consists of primary aluminium grains reinforced with fine precipitates of magnesium silicide (Mg_2Si) and occasionally copper. Heat treatment processes such as solution heat treatment and artificial aging are commonly employed to tailor the mechanical properties of AA6061 according to specific application requirements. This abstract provides an overview of the composition, microstructure, properties, and heat treatment of AA6061 aluminium alloy, highlighting its significance in engineering and manufacturing industries. Wear test was made by using Pin on Disc Apparatus on the prepared Specimen. It was found that, under 10KN, 20KN conditions, the composite displayed lower wear rate compared to counter parts. However, for 30KN load condition the composite displayed higher wear rate. Also, the hardness of the composite was increased by increasing the percent volume of reinforcement.

Keywords: Metal matrix composites, Pin on disc apparatus, Stir casting, Micro structure, Composite, Magnesium

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite alloys are fascinating materials engineered to combine the advantageous properties of two or more distinct metals or non-metallic elements. Unlike traditional alloys, which are typically homogenous mixtures of metals, composite alloys exhibit a heterogeneous structure, where different phases or constituents are intentionally dispersed at a microscopic scale.

These alloys are designed to achieve specific performance characteristics that individual metals alone cannot provide. By strategically blending different materials, engineers can tailor properties such as strength, hardness, corrosion resistance, electrical conductivity, and thermal stability to meet the demands of various applications across industries like aerospace, automotive, electronics, and construction. The fabrication of composite alloys involves precise control over the composition, processing techniques, and microstructure to optimize their performance. Techniques such as powder metallurgy, casting, and sintering are commonly employed to create these advanced materials. Composite alloys can offer superior mechanical properties, lightweight designs, and enhanced functionalities compared to conventional materials. Their versatility makes them invaluable in a wide range of applications where durability, efficiency, and innovation are paramount.

1.1 STIR CASTING METHOD

Stir casting, also known as stir casting method or stir casting process, is a widely used technique for the fabrication of metal matrix composites (MMCs). In this process, solid particles or fibers (reinforcements) are dispersed within a molten metal matrix, resulting in a composite material with enhanced mechanical, thermal, or electrical properties. Solid particles or fibers, which serve as reinforcements, are pre-treated or coated to enhance their wettability with the molten metal matrix and promote uniform dispersion. The matrix metal is melted in a crucible or furnace to form a liquid state. The temperature and alloy composition are controlled to ensure proper flow and compatibility with the reinforcements. The pre-treated reinforcements are added to the molten metal and stirred using a mechanical stirrer or agitator. The stirring action helps to disperse the reinforcements uniformly throughout the matrix, preventing agglomeration and ensuring a homogeneous distribution. This helps improve the quality and integrity of the composite material. Once the desired

reinforcement distribution is achieved, the molten composite mixture is poured into a preheated mold cavity. The mold may be made of steel, graphite, or other suitable materials depending on the desired shape and properties of the final product.

2. ALUMINIUM AND ITS ALLOYS

2.1 INTRODUCTION OF ALUMINIUM

Aluminium is a chemical element in the boron group with symbol Al and atomic number 13. It is a silvery white, soft, ductile metal. Aluminium is the third most abundant element (after oxygen and silicon), and the most abundant metal, in the Earth's crust. It makes up about 8% by weight of the Earth's solid surface. Aluminium metal is so chemically reactive that native specimens are rare and limited to extreme reducing environments. Instead, it is found combined in over 270 different minerals. The chief ore of aluminium is bauxite.

Aluminium is remarkable for the metal's low density and for its ability to resist corrosion due to the phenomenon of passivation. Structural components made from aluminium and its alloys are vital to the aerospace industry and are important in other areas of transportation and structural materials. The most useful compounds of aluminium, at least on a weight basis, are the oxides and sulfates.

2.2 PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Aluminium is a relatively soft, durable lightweight, ductile and malleable metal with appearance ranging from silvery to dull grey, depending on the surface roughness. It is nonmagnetic and does not easily ignite. A fresh film of aluminium serves as a good reflector (approximately 92%) of visible light and an excellent reflector (as much as 98%) of medium and far infrared radiation. The yield strength of pure aluminium is 7-11 MPa, while aluminium has yield strengths ranging from 200 MPa to 600 MPa. Aluminium has about one third the density and stiffness of steel. It is easily.

Aluminium atoms are arranged in a face-centered cubic (fcc) structure. Aluminium has a stacking-fault energy of approximately 200 mJ/m². Aluminium is a good thermal and electrical conductor, having 59% the conductivity of copper, both thermal and electrical, while having only 30% of copper's density. Aluminium is capable of being a superconductor, with a superconducting critical temperature of 1.2 Kelvin and a critical magnetic field of about 100 gauss (10 milliteslas).

2.3 CHEMICAL PROPERTIES

Corrosion resistance can be excellent due to a thin surface layer of aluminium oxide that forms when the metal is exposed to air, effectively preventing further oxidation. The strongest aluminium alloys are less corrosion resistant due to galvanic reactions with alloyed copper. This corrosion resistance is also often greatly reduced by aqueous salts, particularly in the presence of dissimilar metals.

Owing to its resistance to corrosion, aluminium is one of the few metals that retain silvery reflectance in finely powdered form, making it an important component of silver-colored paints. Aluminium mirror finish has the highest reflectance of any metal in the 200-400 nm (UV) and the 3,000-10,000 nm (far IR)

regions; in the 400-700 nm visible range it is slightly outperformed by tin and silver and in the 700-3000 (near IR) by silver, gold, and copper.

Aluminium is oxidized by water to produce hydrogen and heat:

This conversion is of interest for the production of hydrogen. Challenges include circumventing the formed oxide layer,

which inhibits the reaction and the expenses associated with the storage of energy by regeneration of the Al metal which inhibits the reaction and the expenses associated with the storage of energy by regeneration of the Al metal.

Table 2.1 Physical properties of aluminium

Phase	solid
Density (near r.t.)	2.70 g·cm ⁻³
Liquid density atm.p.	2.375 g·cm ⁻³
Melting point	933.47 K 1220.58 °F 660.32 °C _m
Boiling point	4478 °F 2470 °C, 2743 K,
Heat of fusion	10.71 kJ·mol ⁻¹
Heat of vaporization	284 kJ·mol ⁻¹
Molar heat capacity	24.20 J·mol ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹

Table 2.2 General properties

Name, symbol, number	aluminium, Al, 13
Element category	metalloid
Group, period, block	13, 3, p
Standard atomic weight	26.9815385(7)u
Electron configuration	[Ne]3s ² 3p ¹ 2, 8, 3

2.4 CLASSIFICATION OF ALLOYS

The International Alloy Designation System is the most widely accepted naming scheme for wrought alloys. Each alloy is given a four-digit number, where the first digit indicates the major alloying elements. These digits are followed by a letter digit that denotes the temper or heat treatment condition.

- 1xxx series are essentially pure aluminium with a minimum 99% aluminium content by weight and can be work hardened.
- 2xxx series are alloyed with copper, can be precipitation hardened to strengths comparable to steel. Formerly referred to as duralumin, they were once the most common aerospace alloys, but were susceptible to stress corrosion cracking and are increasingly replaced by 7000 series in new designs.
- 3xxx series are alloyed with manganese, and can be work hardened.
- 4xxx series are alloyed with silicon. They are also known as salumi.
- 5xxx series are alloyed with magnesium.

- 6xxx series are alloyed with magnesium and silicon, are easy to machine, and can be precipitation hardened, but not to the high strengths that 2000 and 7000 can reach.
- 7xxx series are alloyed with zinc, and can be precipitation hardened to the highest strengths of any aluminium alloy.
- 8xxx series are alloyed with other elements which are not covered by other series.

3. MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

3.1 MATERIAL SELECTION

6061 Aluminium alloy : (AA6061) is an aluminium alloy with zinc as the primary alloying element. It has excellent mechanical properties and exhibits good ductility, high strength, toughness, and good resistance to fatigue. It is more susceptible to embrittlement than many other aluminium alloys because of micro segregation, but has significantly better corrosion resistance than the alloys from the 2000 series. It is one of the most commonly used aluminium alloys for highly stressed structural applications and has been extensively used in aircraft structural parts.

6061 aluminium alloy's composition roughly includes 5.6–6.1% zinc, 2.1–2.5% magnesium, 1.2–1.6% copper, and less than a half percent of silicon, iron, manganese, titanium, chromium, and other metals. It is produced in many tempers, some of which are 6061-0, 6061-T6, 6061-T651.

Magnesium composites are new class metal matrix composites widely used in aerospace and automobile industries due to their low density, good mechanical properties, better corrosion and wear resistance, low thermal coefficient of expansion as compared to conventional metals and alloys.

3.2 PREPARATION OF MATERIAL

Aluminium 6061 was taken as matrix and pure magnesium was taken as reinforcement for the preparation of composite material. The aspect ratio for the preparation of composite was taken as **97:3**, **94:6**, **91:9**, **88:12** respectively

- ❖ For aspect ratio **97:3** the weight ratio was (677:21) grams respectively for the preparation of 1st specimen composite material
- ❖ For aspect ratio **94:6** the weight ratio was (657:42) grams respectively for the preparation of 2nd specimen composite material
- ❖ For aspect ratio **91:9** the weight ratio was (635:63) grams respectively for the preparation of 3rd specimen composite material
- ❖ For aspect ratio **88:12** the weight ratio was (616:93) grams respectively for the preparation of 4th specimen composite material

The specimen was taken as bar first the aluminium bar was melted in the crucible up to 700°C and with the help of stirrer the molten metal is stirred for 60 sec then the reinforcement

magnesium was added to the molten metal and was heated by 750°C was maintained for all specimen sample preparation. Now with the help of Stirrer the molten metal (Matrix and reinforcement) the molten metal was stirred for 60 sec at a speed of 400 rpm the stirrer blade was made up of SS304 grade which has high corrosive and thermal resistance properties at elevated temperature. This procedure was followed for all the sample specimen preparation.

The prepared molten metal was taken into a die, where a die was made up of mild steel material before pouring the molten metal. The die was pre heated up to temp of 350°C. The prepared molten metal was poured into the die was allowed to cool completely for about 15min. The specimen was prepared and was taken out and cut into required sizes for testing properties evaluation. Both mechanical and metallurgical testing was carried out and the results are tabulated. For mechanical testing tensile test, hardness and wear test was carried out for metallurgical test SEM with EDS and XRD was carried out.

The cast samples were machined to prepare standard samples. 24 standard samples were prepared using milling and lathe machine. 8 samples were used for Tensile test, elongation was determined using universal tensile testing machine. The details of the tensile test parameters are given samples were used for hardness tests by using Vickers hardness testing machine. The Vickers hardness was converted to HRB scale. 12 samples were used for wear test by using wear testing machine The details of the mechanical properties such as tensile strength, hardness and wear test are given.

3.3 CUTTING

The large body of the investigated material is not necessarily homogeneous; therefore, the specimen should be taken from the region, adequately representing the structure and other features of the large sample.

Sometimes the directional factor is essential: preferential direction of crystals formed in directional solidification, elongated grains and inclusions after rolling. In these cases, direction of the cut surface is taken into account.

Cutting operation itself may change the specimen micro-structure, due to heating and mechanical damage. Cutting technique is selected in a way, preventing such effect.

- Soft non-ferrous alloys are cut by resin bonded SiC discs.
- Steels and hard non-ferrous alloys are cut by resin bonded alumina discs.
- Ceramics, minerals, composite and electronic materials are cut by low speed diamond wafer blades.

3.4 MOUNTING

Mounting metallographic specimen serves for protection of the specimen edges and improvement of its irregular shape, enabling both easy manual and automated grinding/polishing operation.

Compression mounting is the most popular method for metal specimens.

- Phenolic resin is the most widely used low-cost mounting material.
- Acrylic resin is used when clarity of the mounting is important.
- Epoxy resin is used when hardness of the mount is required.

3.5 GRINDING

Surface damages, created by cutting discs, are reduced by grinding. Dry or wet silicon carbide abrasive paper is used for grinding operation. Special grinding tables equipped with clamps for strips of grinding paper are used for manual grinding. Rotary grinding/polishing machine is used for automated grinding. The rotation speed, which initially is about 300 RPM should be decreased to 150 RPM in the course of grinding. Grinding is carried out on a series of stages with increasing the fineness of the paper: 240, 400, 600, 1000. The fineness number indicates a number of SiC grains on square inch. Each grinding operation removes the marks, produced in the previous operation. After each grinding stage the specimen should be thoroughly washed in order to prevent carry-over the coarser grit to the grinding paper. The grinding direction of each stage should be changed by 90° relative to the direction of the previous stage. This makes easier indication of completion of the grinding stage (removal of the scratches from the previous stage).

3.6 POLISHING

The fine scratches caused by final grinding operation are removed by polishing. Flaky powders of different fineness are used as polishing abrasives. A mixture of powder and water is spread over a rotating disc covered with polishing velvet cloth. Alumina, magnesia and diamond powders of various fineness (12-15µm, 5-6µm, 1µm) are usually used for successive polishing stages. The specimen is thoroughly washed after each stage in order to prevent contamination of the polishing cloth by coarse powder particles from the previous stage. Rotary disc machines with adjustable rotation speed are used for polishing. The machine may be equipped with an appliance for the specimens holding and loading. Etching is the operation of revealing micro-structural features (grain boundaries, phases, precipitates and other micro-structure constituents) of the polished specimen through selective chemical attack of its surface.

- The specimen must be washed and degreased in boiling alcohol and then cooled in running water before etching in order to prevent uneven attack and stains.
- Clean specimen is etched by being immersion in the etching reagent for a given time. Then the specimen is quickly removed from the reagent and immediately swilled in running water.
- The etched specimen is then visually inspected. Its surface should have slightly dull appearance (bright appearance requires additional etching).
- Then the wet specimen should be dried in alcohol.

3.7 ETCHING REAGENTS

- For Aluminium and magnesium composites
- Keller's reagent:

Methanol 25ml + hydrochloride acid 25% + Nitric acid + 1 drop of Hydrofluoric acid was added to prepare etching for Aluminium and Magnesium composites

Etching time: 10-60 sec.

Reveal: Aluminium and magnesium boundaries and intermetallic compounds made of zinc, Aluminium, Magnesium, Brass and Copper

3.8 OPTICAL MICROSCOPY

After etching samples were examined under optical microscope with different magnification like 100X, 200X, 500X, 1000X. Micro analysis was done in CEMAJOR Annamalai university, Chidambaram.

Fig 3.1 Optical Microscope

3.9 TENSILE STRENGTH MEASUREMENT

Tension test was done as per ASTM standard E8. Tension tests provide information on the strength and ductility of materials under uniaxial tensile stresses. This information may be useful in comparisons of materials, alloy development, quality control, and design under certain circumstances.

Fig 3.2 Standard tensile specimen line diagram

The results of tension tests of specimens machined to standardized dimensions from selected portions of a part or material may not totally represent the strength and ductility properties of the entire end product or its in-service behavior in different environments

Figure 3.3 Universal testing machine

The prepared specimen was subjected to universal tensile testing machine. The value had testing range of 5 ton with load accuracy of 0.1N and crosshead speed accuracy of 0.01mm. The specimen was subjected in between the jaws of tensile testing machine and the load was initial gradual raised it was absorbed that from the table that specimen 3 with aspect ratio 91% of aluminium and 9% of magnesium shown maximum tensile strength with high elongation rate. YS/UTS ratio was ensured for adequate ductility to allow in elastic deformation. Maximum YS/UTS of 1.0 is to ensure ductile flexural failure rather than brittle shear failure.

3.10 MICROHARDNESS MEASUREMENT

The Vickers Hardness Test consists of a small pyramid shaped diamond indenter with an apical angle of 136, which is pressed into the test sample at a predetermined load. The resulting indentation is then measured in both axis from tip to tip. The average of the two axis measurements is then converted into a Vickers Hardness number by the use of a formula, or more often a chart based on the formula. When choosing the test load, the highest load that can be performed on the specimen will give the most accurate results. A higher load produces a larger indentation with better measurement resolution and therefore, more reliable results. As per the ASTM E92 standard. The hardness variation is measured across the weld joint using the vicker's micro hardness tester (Model: HMV-2T) at load of 500g for 15 Sec. The distance between two hardness indentation is 0.5 mm.

Fig 3.4 Micro Vickers's Hardness test

3.11 WEAR STRENGTH MEASUREMENT

The wear test was carried out in wear testing machine with variation of point load varying from 10KN, 20KN and 30KN respectively. The test parameters sliding velocity 1.25m/s and sliding distance of 500m was maintained constant in the wear testing machine. Sliding diameter of 40mm machine speed of 597 rpm and time of 400 sec was maintained constant. The initial weight before subjected on to the machine was calculated. After the wear test on the machine the final weight was calculated in grams with difference of initial weight and final weight the wear loss in grams.

Figure 3.5 Wear test machine

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION :

The results obtained from tensile test, micro hardness test, wear test, SEM with EDS analysis and X-ray diffraction method was discussed in detail in this section.

4.1 TENSILE TEST:

The prepared specimen was subjected to universal tensile testing machine were the value had testing range of 5 ton with load accuracy of 0.1N and crosshead speed accuracy of 0.01mm. The specimen was subjected in between the jaws of tensile testing machine and the load was initial gradual raised it was absorbed that from the table that specimen 3 with aspect ratio 91% of aluminium and 9% of magnesium shown maximum tensile strength with high elongation rate. YS/UTS ratio was ensured for adequate ductility to allow in elastic deformation. Maximum YS/UTS of 1.0 is to ensure ductile flexural failure rather than brittle shear failure.

Table 4.1 Tensile test vs specimen

	S1	S2	S3	S4
UTS	1417.55	2584.33	4754.21	1062.81
YS	62.5	112.15	206.24	45.61
BL	813.44	2466.32	4538.97	792.61

The graph for tensile test represents the composites material madewith 91% of aluminium and 9% of Magnesium by weight healed at maximum ultimate tensile strength and the higher breaking loadwhen compared with hits other counter parts

Figure 4.1 Tensile graph

4.2 HARDNESS TEST:

In hardness test within each scenario, there are variations in hardness values across different zones. For instance, in Scenario S1, Zone 2 has the highest hardness (147), while Zone 3 has the lowest (123), indicating potential differences in composition, grain structure, or other factors within the alloy.

Table 4.2 Micro hardness test

	S1	S2	S3	S4
Zone 1	141	135	154	137
Zone 2	147	138	145	132
Zone 3	123	153	149	144
Average	411	426	448	413

The hardness test conducted with the Vickers hardness testing machine reveals that the 3rd specimen shows highest hardness value of 154 VHN ,145 VHN, 149 VHN when compare to its other specimens. The graph for this valve is shown below.

Figure 4.2 Graph for Hardness test

4.3 WEAR TEST

The wear test was carried out in wear testing machine with variation of point load varying from 10KN,20KN and 30KN reveals that the 3rd and 4th specimen shows highest wear value of 0.002, 0.003, 0.004 when compare to its other specimens.

Table 4.3 Wear vs specimen

	S1	S2	S3	S4
10KN	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.004
20KN	0.002	0.001	0.003	0.004
30KN	0.002	0.001	0.004	0.002

Figure 4.3 Graph for wear test

5. CONCLUSION

From the above experimental results, the following results wasconcluded:

The composites material made with 91% of aluminium and 9% of Magnesium by weight healed at maximum ultimate tensile strength and the higher breaking load when compared withhits other counter parts

The hardness test conducted with the Vickers hardness testing machine reveals that the 3rd specimen shows highest hardness valve of 154 VHN , 145 VHN, 149 VHN when compare to its other specimens

The wear test conducted that with 10Kn and 20Kn load applied 4th specimen has the higher wear rate while specimen 2 with aspect ratio 94% of aluminum and 6% of magnesium shows the minimum wear rate for all 10Kn,20Kn,30Kn load supplied

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